

Open Meets Hardware

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Open Source Hardware Association

Overview

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.ATLAS

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Challenges

- Thinking about open sourcing your Intellectual Property when patenting has been so ingrained in our culture is like moving the Titanic.
- Each field has nuances in the source, so each field needs a community of thought leaders to think through how and what to open and apply best practices
- We need to redefine what success looks like in academia

Generalizations: Industry v. academia

- Academics number one goal is not revenue - and it shouldn't be.
- Many, many successful open hardware companies are in the multi-millions of dollars, there is a business model
- People do not buy things based on the number of patents it has and not everyone wants to be a producer - some just want to consume - however being driven by patents means many will rebuild the wheel
- The number of oshw companies is growing willing to partner with academics if there is a revenue stream - however sometimes science has a smaller base of buyers in many cases and precision of reproducibility is paramount in academia and not always in industry

Opportunities

- If you are not in electronics or 3D printing, you are a foundational member of bringing open hardware to a new field
- Because we are only ten years old, there is a unique opportunity to drive policy and regulations and be proactive with policy makers, rather than have policy made that is reactive to the open hardware community
- OSHWA can help by partnering to create best practices in various fields, and assist in measuring and redefining success for this field

Thank You

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